

WOMEN IN AGRICULTURE AND COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT: A STUDY OF BEKWARRA WOMEN IN CROSS RIVER STATE

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ABSTRACT

Blessed with abundant land and water resources, Nigeria's agricultural sector has a high potential for growth. African women play a central role in the continent's agricultural sector. Bekwarra women are women who are born into or married into Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State and they are known for great involvement in agricultural practices. Lack of recognition of Bekwarra women in agriculture by the government and other relevant agencies have prompted this quantitative survey research which sought to examine the role of Bekwara women in agriculture in the development of Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State. Women In Development Theory was adopted for theoretical framework. A total of 396 sample size made of purposively selected mature men and women of 30 years and above were engaged for the study. Data were collected through the use of questionnaire and hypothesis tested through the use of SPSS. Findings of the study shown that there exist a high positive relationship between Bekwarra women involvement in farming (EWF) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL) which was ascertain by the Pearson Product Moment Correlation ($r = +.892, p < 0.001$ significance level) between the two variables, and there exists a high relationship between Bekwarra women involvement in trading (BWT) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL) which was ascertain by the Pearson product Moment Correlation ($r = +.893, p < 0.001$ significance level) between the two variables. It was conclude that the development of Bekwarra Local Government Area has witnessed the involvement and contributions of Bekwarra women in agriculture. Among others, the researcher recommended that Modern seedlings and other farming chemicals including fertilizer should be made accessible ot Bekwarra women by the non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and government in order to promote more food production by the Bekwarra women.

Keywords: Bekwarra women, agriculture, community development, farming and trading

INTRODUCTION

According to the FAO (2020), agriculture remains the foundation of the Nigerian economy, providing livelihoods for most Nigerians, and generating millions of jobs especially in the rural areas of the nation (Adeite, 2022), with capacity to eradicate poverty (Peters and Bassey, 2019). Agriculture is pivotal to the realization of the Millennium Development goals in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) as it contributes 70% of employment, 40% of exports and one-third of Gross Domestic Products (GDP) (Anandajayasekerm, 2008). Enhancing African agricultural productivity is a prerequisite for eradicating African poverty and associated food and nutrition insecurity. Anandajayasekerm (2008), further posit that over the past four decades, the international consensus on the importance of agriculture in economic development has varied from very high (until 1980s), to very low (1990s) to the current rediscovery. According to World Development Report (2008) cited in OECD-FAO (2016), it has been increasingly recognized that in the 21st century, for the agriculture based countries, agriculture continues to be a fundamental instrument for sustainable development and poverty reduction. The agricultural sector heavily influence economic development in most countries in Sub-Saharan Africa (OECD-FAO, 2016). From 1990 to 2013, the total value of agricultural production, measured in constant US dollars, increased by 130%. The crop sector dominates total agricultural production value, accounting on average for almost 85% of total production value over the 24-year period. This share differs across the region, ranging from 53% in Southern Africa, to more than 90% in Western Africa (OECD-FAO, 2016).

Blessed with abundant land and water resources, Nigeria's agricultural sector has a high potential for growth, but this potential is not being realized ((Ehui and Tsigas, 2009). Productivity is low and basically stagnant. Farming systems, which are mostly small in scale, are still predominantly subsistence-based and for the most part depend on the vagaries of the weather. The country's vast irrigation potential remains largely unexploited. Most farmers produce mainly food crops using traditional extensive cultivation methods, while commercial agriculture based on modern technologies and purchased inputs remains underdeveloped. The capacity of the agricultural research system has eroded in recent years, as has that of the extension service, so, even when improved technologies are available, often they fail to reach farmers. Farmers' lack of technical knowledge is compounded by deficiencies in input distribution systems, which limit the timely availability of improved seed, fertilizer, crop chemicals, and machinery (Ehui and Tsigas, 2009).

According to Buvinic and Mehra (1990), before 1970, analyses of women's roles in Third World agriculture were found mostly in ethnographic studies of traditional societies. Most retirees especially women are engaged in agriculture (Ononkpono *et al*, 2020), Ester Boserup, an economist, according to Buvinic and Mehra (1990) deserves full credit for placing this subject squarely within economic development. In 1970 she presented the first comprehensive, empirically based analysis of women's participation in agriculture and linked the evolution of farming systems to population pressures, technological change in agriculture, and the participation of women in the labour force (Buvinic and Mehra, 1990). Boserup as cited by Buvinic and Mehra (1990) distinguished three types of agricultural systems: female, male, and mixed. Female farming systems in some countries in Africa and Latin America and in certain areas of India are characterized by slash and burn agriculture, communal land ownership, and the use of the hoe (Buvinic and Mehra, 1990). Except for land

clearing, most of the work is done by women, who support themselves and their children. These women tend to be economically independent and mobile. If they generate an agricultural surplus, they engage in trade to supplement their subsistence earnings with cash income (Buvinic and Mehra, 1990). Women described as farmers, livestock owners, workers and entrepreneurs within the sector, consistently experience limited access to productive resources, compared to their male counterparts (Njobe and Kaaria, 2015).

Male farming systems, found in Asia, are based on land ownership, settled production patterns, and the use of draft animals and the plough. Field labour is done almost entirely by men and is supplemented by hired labour; if women contribute to farming at all, it is during harvest time or at other peak periods. Women are often secluded and are dependent on men for economic support. Mixed farming, which follows and shares many of the characteristics of male farming systems, emerges with rapidly growing populations. Increasing land pressure requires year-round intensive cultivation and multiple cropping, which are facilitated with irrigation. Labour demand is high and, despite social norms to the contrary, women are drawn into such tasks as weeding, transplanting, and harvesting (Buvinic and Mehra, 1990).

African women play a central role in the continent's agriculture sector (Njobe and Kaaria, 2015) and agriculture has been a bedrock for most community development projects (Atairet *et al*, 2021). As the backbone of the sector women represent 52% of the total population in the sector and are responsible for approximately 50% of the agricultural labour on farms in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (Njobe and Kaaria, 2015). African women also produce 60% to 80% of the continent's food. Counter intuitively, African women, persistently remain an untapped opportunity in agriculture, their level and quality of participation does not accrue to sustainable socio-economic development benefits (Njobe and Kaaria, 2015). According to Asaju and Adagba, (2013) who observed that in the food processing and cottage industries in three Zaria villages, 90 percent of the women were involved in at least one food processing activity or the other. United Nation's report which reveals that 60 – 90 percent of the agricultural labour forces are women and they produce two-third of the food crops (Asaju and Adagba, 2013) Hassan and Silong (2008) posit that women have long been the mainstay of national development right from the community level and are heavily involved in community initiatives in various forms.

Boserup as cited by Buvinic and Mehra (1990), attributes the disappearance of female farming systems to population pressure and the introduction of cash crops during the colonial period. Population pressure caused a shift to permanent agriculture. The plough replaced the hoe, ploughing became men's work, arguably because it required physical strength and/or physical mobility, and men took over many of the farming activities. For example, in colonial Africa, European administrators and technical advisers introduced cash crops and modern agricultural technologies to men. Men, therefore, took credit for developing a highly productive export-oriented farming sector while women were left behind in the traditional low-yielding subsistence sector. As a consequence, women lost control over farming as well as the economic autonomy derived from farming. Without question, Boserup's work provided much of the substance for the increased attention to women's issues by the United Nations, development agencies, and nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) starting in 1975, when an International Women's Year conference was held in Mexico City (Buvinic and Mehra, 1990). Until this conference, international donors, national governments and NGOs

had channelled development resources to women only in their roles as mothers and homemakers. Women's roles as economic producers are more visible as farmers as well as wage labourers, though they had been ignored.

Bekwarra women are women who are born into or married into Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State. Bekwarra Local Government Area is in the Northern Senatorial District of Cross River State. There are ten political wards in the local government and these are; Abuochiche, Afrike Ochagbe, Afrike Okpeche, Benten, Gakem, Abi-Aragin, Nyanya, Otukpuru, Otukpuru, Ugboro and Ukpah. Bekwarra Local Government Area has its headquarters at Abuochiche. It is bounded in the north by Benue State, South by Ogoja Local Government Area, East by Obudu Local Government Area and West by Yala Local Government Area. The major population groups of the local government area are Ujia, Unwapu, Unwagba Oli West, Oti East, Eya Aba, Beten, Uduo, Eya Adie, Ika-Ichia, Udomu, Atibulum, Afrike-Okpeche, Okpeche, Ikachor, Ugboro, Ukpah, Anyikang, Abuochiche, and Ochagbe. The major economic activities in the area include agriculture, cattle/goat and poultry rearing, and trading. Majority of the indigenes are farmers whose produce are sold within and outside the state. The area has very rich cultural heritage. The major traditional festival is the New Yam Festival held during the first week of September yearly. The traditional market days are; Udama, Ugbada, Uchagu, Ugidi, and Achanya.

Variations in women's participation in agricultural work depend on supply and demand factors linked to economic growth and agricultural modernization (Buvinic and Mehra, 1990). The demand for female farm labour has also increased with male labour migration and with agricultural policies that foster the development of agribusiness, in which women comprise the bulk of the work force. The time women spend in farm activities supplementing male labour as well as farming their own plots has increased notably among small farmers. In Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State, Bekwarra women are known for agricultural business. Bekwarra women are known for hard work when it comes to land cultivation, seedling planting, weeding, harvesting, processing and marketing of agricultural produce. The Bekwarra women are involve in agriculture from A to Z processes which implies that they are involve from the land clearing to marketing. The case of the Bekwarra women in contributing to the development of the Bekwarra Local Government Area through agriculture has been the case posited by the Buvinic and Mehra (1990), that despite women's extensive and varied participation in agriculture, they continue to have less access than do men to modern agricultural inputs. In addition, they are not given the recognition deserved, and the empowerment required to foster the community development through which agriculture in the hands of the Bekwarra women have projected over generations of the Bekwarra people. On this background, this research paper sought to examine the role of Bekwarra women in the development of Bekwarra communities in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Women In Development Theory

The term "women in development" came into use in the early 1970s, after the publication of Ester Boserup's *Women's Role in Economic Development* (1970). Boserup was the first to systematically delineate on a global level the sexual division of labour that

existed in agrarian economies. She analysed the changes that occurred in traditional agricultural practices as societies became modernized and examined the differential impact of those changes on the work done by men and women. She concluded that in sparsely populated regions where shifting agriculture is practiced, women tend to do the majority of agricultural work (Buvinic, 1986).

The term "Women In Development" was initially used by the women's committee of the Washington, D.C. chapter of the Society for International Development as part of a deliberate strategy to bring the new evidence generated by Boserup and others to the attention of American policymakers (Maguire 1984). A set of common concerns, loosely labelled "Women in Development" or WID began to be articulated by American liberal feminists who advocated legal and administrative changes to ensure that women would be better integrated into economic systems (Jaquette, 1982). They placed primary emphasis on egalitarianism and on the development of strategies and action programs aimed at minimizing the disadvantages of women in the productive sector and ending discrimination against them.

Under the rubric of Women In Development, the position of women in various sectors of the economy for the first time was studied separate from that of men. The recognition that women's experience of development and of societal change differed from that of men was institutionalized and it became legitimate for research to focus specifically on women's experiences and perceptions. None the less, the Women In Development approach was based on several assumptions which were at odds with critical trends in social sciences research in the 1970s (Buvinic, 1986).

Women In Development approach also focused exclusively on the productive aspects of women's work, ignoring or minimizing their productive side of women's lives. Thus, Women In Development projects typically have been income-generating activities where women are taught a particular skill or craft and sometimes are organized into marketing cooperatives. Frequently a welfare outlook is added to projects and women are taught aspects of hygiene, literacy or child care at the same time (Buvinic, 1986).

METHODOLOGY

This quantitative survey research was conducted in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State. One community was selected from Abuochiche, Afrike Ochagbe, Afrike Okpeche, Benten, Gakem, Abi-Aragin, Nyanya, Otukpuru, Otukpuru, Ugboro and Ukpah political ward of the local government area respectively. Only mature men and women of 30 years and above were purposively and randomly selected from selected villages within the 10 wards. Data were collected through the use of questionnaire from 396 sample size. Data gathered by the researcher were analysed descriptively through testing of hypothesis with the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULTS

Roles of Bekwarra women in farming and development of Bekwarra Local Government Area

Pearson Product Moment Correlation through SPSS was used for testing hypothesis one (1) which sought to establish whether there is a relationship between Bekwarra women

involvement in farming (EWF) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL) as presented in the table below.

Table 1: Showing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis between Bekwarra women involvement in farming (BWF) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL)

Bekwarra women involvement in farming (EWF) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL) (*n* = 396)

		DBL	EWF
DBL	Pearson Correlation	1	.892**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	396	396
BWF	Pearson Correlation	.892**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	396	396

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 shows that the Pearson product moment correlation of Bekwarra women involvement in farming (EWF) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL) was highly positive and statistically significant ($r = .892, p < .001$). Hence, the null hypothesis of hypothesis one which stated that there is no relationship between Bekwarra women involvement in farming and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area was rejected. This implies that Bekwarra women involvement in farming (BWF) contribute to development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL) in Cross River State, Nigeria. Hence, Bekwarra women involvement in farming has led to the economic growth of Bekwarra Local Government Area through provision of food stuffs and fruits that have positioned Bekwarra Local Government Area in inter-local government and inter-state trades for decades, and this have served as sources of revenue for the Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL).

The high positive relationship between the variables is indicated by the Pearson product moment correlation (r) which is $+ .892$ in accordance to the rules which states that there exists a high positive or negative correlation when $r = \pm .70$ to $\pm .90$. In the case of the correlation (r) between Bekwarra women involvement in farming (BWF) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL), $r = + .892$ which supports a high positive statistical significance between the two variables and the statistical significance is lower than 0.01 level of significance at 0.000.

Bekwarra women involvement in trading and development of Bekwarra Local Government Area

Pearson Product Moment Correlation through SPSS was used for testing hypothesis two (2) which sought to establish whether there is a relationship between Bekwarra women

involvement in trading (BWT) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL).

Table 2: Showing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis between Bekwarra women involvement in trading (BWT) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL)

Bekwarra women involvement in trading (BWT) and development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL) (*n* = 396)

		DBL	BWT
DBL	Pearson Correlation	1	.893**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	396	396
BWT	Pearson Correlation	.893**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	396	396

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows that the Pearson product moment correlation of Bekwarra women involvement in trading (BWT) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL) was highly positive and statistically significant ($r = .893$, $p < .001$). Hence, the null hypothesis of hypothesis two which stated that there is no relationship between Bekwarra women involvement in trading (BWT) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL) was rejected. This implies that Bekwarra women involvement in trading (BWT) contribute to development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL) in Cross River State, Nigeria. Hence, Bekwarra women involvement in trading has led to the economic growth of Bekwarra Local Government Area through provision of financial resources from family level to local government level in terms of revenue generation through the inter-local government and inter-state trades which Bekwarra Local Government Area has engaged in for decades.

The high positive relationship between the variables is indicated by the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) which is $+ .893$. In accordance to the rules which states that there existS a high positive or negative correlation when $r = \pm .70$ to $\pm .90$. In the case of the correlation (r) between Bekwarra women involvement in trading (BWT) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL), $r = + .893$ which supports a high positive statistical significance between the two variables and the statistical significance is lower than 0.01 level of significance at 0.000.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of the study are discussed according to answers to the research objectives and analysis of corresponding hypotheses as follows:

Bekwarra women involvement in farming and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area

Findings of the study on the first objective of the research work shows that there exists a high positive relationship between Bekwarra women involvement in farming (EWF) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL). This was ascertain by the Pearson Product Moment Correlation ($r = +.892$, $p < 0.001$ significance level) between the two variables. Finding of study according to the researcher showed that Bekwarra women involvement in farming has positioned Bekwarra Local Government Area in development through generation of resources and income for economic and other forms of development in the local government area. Emergence from findings of the study revealed that Bekwarra women involvement in farming has led to the economic growth of Bekwarra Local Government Area through provision of food stuffs and fruits that have positioned Bekwarra Local Government Area in inter-local government and inter-state trades for decades, and this has served as sources of revenue for the Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL) in Cross River State. This finding agrees the United Nation's report which reveals that 60 – 90 percent of the agricultural labour forces are women and they produce two-third of the food crops (Asaju and Adagba, 2013). This finding is given credence by Hassan and Silong (2008) posit that women have long been the mainstay of national development right from the community level and are heavily involved in community initiatives in various forms.

Bekwarra women involvement in trading and development of Bekwarra Local Government Area

Emergence from the study findings on objective two is that there exists a high relationship between Bekwarra women involvement in trading (BWT) and Development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL). This was ascertain by the Pearson product Moment Correlation ($r = +.893$, $p < 0.001$ significance level) between the two variables. This implies trading is one of the foremost occupations of the Bekwarra women, and Bekwarra women involvement in trading (BWT) has contribute to the economic growth and revenue generation for the development of Bekwarra Local Government Area (DBL) in Cross River State, Nigeria. Hence, Bekwarra women involvement in trading has led to the economic growth of Bekwarra Local Government Area through provision of financial resources from family level to local government level in term of revenue generation through the inter-local government and inter-state trades which Bekwarra Local Government Area has engaged in for decades. Further findings showed that large population of women in Bekwarra Local Government Area are involve in food processing and trading of such food items lke garri, foofoo, plantain, bannana, groundnut, and other such raw and processed food stuffs. These have place Bekwarra Local Government Area in the path of inter-local government and inter-states trades. This finding is in agreement with Asaju and Adagba, (2013) who observed that in the food processing and cottage industries in three Zaria villages, 90 percent of the women were involved in at least one food processing activity or the other.

CONCLUSION

Women have played impactful roles in the development of every community in

Bekwarra Local Government Area. The development of Bekwarra Local Government Area has witnessed the involvement and contributions of Bekwarra women in agriculture. Bekwarra women have been involved in the economic development of their local government area through farming and trading of raw and processed food stuffs within the Bekwarra Local Government Area, other local government areas within Cross River State and beyond. These involvements have created various avenues for resources and revenue generation from family, the local government and national levels. The development of Bekwarra Local Government Area has the contributions of the women at the centre piece within the various sectors of the economy and aspects of development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made from the findings of this research:

- i. Bekwarra Local Government Area should endeavour to empower women with needed farming machineries and loans to encourage and promote more farming involvement by the women.
- ii. Government should create more modern marketing facilities for more resourceful trading by the women in order to create more effective revenue generations for the local government area.
- iii. Women should be given opportunities to take up ownership of landed properties in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State. This will promote more involvement of women in agro-allied business.
- iv. Bekwarra Local Government Council should endeavour to make judicious use of the revenue generated through the market women to construct good roads in Bekwarra in order to enable easy transportation of farm produce from the farm to the market by the women.
- v. Modern seedlings and other farming chemicals including fertilizer should be made accessible to the Bekwarra women by the non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and government in order to promote more food production by the Bekwarra women.

REFERENCES

- Adeite, A. (2022). "Agriculture in Nigeria: 7 Interesting Facts & Statistics". *Babban Gona*.
- Anandajayasekerm, P. (2008). Agriculture for Development in Africa: Options and Way Forward. *African Union Bulletin*. 1(4): 2 -20
- Asaju, K. and Adagba, S. O. (2013). Women Participation in National Development in Nigeria: Imperative of Education. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 3(1): 57-69.
- Ataire, A. C., Mboho, K. S. and Aborh, K. B. (2021) Constituency Project and Community Participation for Sustainable Rural Development: Experience from Selected Local Government of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *African Multidisciplinary Journal of Development (AMJD)*, Kampala International University, Vol. 10, ISSUE 3, UGANDA, pp 60-73.
- Buvinic, M. and Mehra, R. (1990). Women in Agriculture: What Development Can Do. Retrieved online on 20th August, 2023.
- Ehui, S. and Tsigas, M. (2009). The Role of Agriculture in Nigeria's Economic Growth: A General Equilibrium Analysis. Retrieved online as Pdf on 20th August, 2023.

- Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations (2020). *www.fao.org*. Retrieved on 20th August, 2023.
- Hassan, Z. and Silong, A. D. (2008). Women Leadership and Community Development. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 23 (3); 361-372.
- Njobe, B. and Kaaria, S. (2015). Women and Agriculture: The Untapped Opportunity in the Wave of Transformation. United Nation Economics Commission for Africa. Retrieved online on 20th August, 2023.
- OECD-FAO (2016). Agriculture in Sub-Saharan Africa: Prospects and challenges for the next decade. *Agricultural Outlook 2016-2025*. Retrieved online on 20th August, 2023.
- Ononokpono, D. N., Peters, M. I. and Usoro, N. A. (2020) Determinants of Health Care Utilization among Retirees in Rural Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *The Nigerian Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*. 18(1): 71-86
- Peters, M. I. and Aniekan E. Bassey (2019). Ethnography Studies and Poverty Eradication toward Achieving Sustainable Development Goals in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Sociology on the Ascent. A Festschrift in Honour of Professor Ekong Edem Ekong, OFR, FNRS*. Essoh and Usoro (Eds). A Publication of the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Uyo. Brainspec Publishers, Uyo. 38 – 53